

THE DEVELOPMENT OF INQUIRY-BASED GENERAL CHEMISTRY LEARNING MODULE FOR GRADE 11 STEM STUDENTS AT CAVITE STATE UNIVERSITY-CCAT CAMPUS A.Y 2024-2025

Trazares, Marco Paolo M.¹, Quemuel, Khate Irish P.², Obejas, John Melo F.³, Candare, Arcie Jay Ar O.⁴, Jose, Leonard Vincent E.⁵

¹rc.marcopaolo.trazares@cvsu.edu.ph; <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4528-576X>

²rc.khateirish.quemuel@cvsu.edu.ph; <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-5612-6716>

³rc.johnmelo.obejas@cvsu.edu.ph; <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7258-0281>

⁴rc.arciejayar.candare@cvsu.edu.ph; <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-4558-9652>

⁵rc.leonardvincent.jose@cvsu.edu.ph; <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-8596-0804>

Abstract

Inquiry-based learning module is a teaching tool that is capable of giving the students deep and meaningful learning experiences. This also supports differentiated learning which adapts the students' diverse learning style. The main objectives of this study were to develop an inquiry-based learning module for Grade 11 STEM students, to assess the development of Grade 11 STEM students' critical thinking skills in terms of identifying and defining problems, differentiation of concepts, idea evaluation, and to formulate a suggestion for using inquiry-based learning module for other topics of general chemistry. This study used developmental research method. The researchers gathered the data through the use of pre-test, post-test and survey questionnaires, as it is the most effective method of collecting data that has been distributed to the Grade 11 STEM students of Cavite State University-CCAT Campus. The findings indicated that the steps in developing an inquiry-based learning module for Grade 11 STEM students is consisted of five (5) major procedures which are the information gathering, designing, development, disseminate, and recommendation. Based on the t-test results, idea evaluation and refinement showed the highest significant difference ($t = -2.20$), followed by identifying and defining problems ($t = -1.47$), and differentiating concepts ($t = -1.33$). These results indicate that students demonstrated the most improvement in idea evaluation and refinement. Survey responses revealed that the majority of students were satisfied with the module. They strongly agreed that it provided deeper conceptual understanding, fostered critical thinking through guided and independent inquiry, and encouraged active participation in inquiry-based tasks. However, a few students expressed uncertainty about pursuing further inquiry-based learning modules. This study highlights the effectiveness of the developed inquiry-based learning module in enhancing critical thinking skills.

Keywords: *Inquiry-based, Learning module, STEM, General Chemistry, Critical thinking.*

Introduction

Assisting students acquire the required skills, teachers ought to foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and active learning in the classroom. However, the implementation of inquiry-based learning remains vague in the literature, and there are a variety of learning models for it (Bogador et al., 2024). Implementing inquiry can be a challenging endeavor for a number of reasons (Aldrich, 2020). Traditional teaching in the laboratory gives more emphasis on a cookbook approach. The teacher is guiding students with explicit, step-by-step instructions to achieve specific predetermined outcomes and focuses only on facts (Partanen, 2020). Ineffective teaching methods in science make students simply memorize facts for examinations without understanding how to use basic science concepts in daily life, posing a significant challenge for the country's ability to compete globally in this era of rapid advancement in science and technology (Farooq et al., 2023). In new society, students' critical thinking skills are crucial for their future development (Yu et al., 2024). Activities that are exciting should emerge more frequently for positive attitudes of learners (Herwinarso et al., 2023).

Inquiry-based learning should be interconnected to materials that being utilized for more interactions (Aldrich, 2020). Advent teaching strategies such as inquiry and learner centered should be consider the needs of students through improvised teaching method that can enhance students (Farooq et al., 2023). Perception of majority of students to IBL are positive (Herwinarso et al., 2023), thus, some of them prefer selected auditory and visual learning (Bogador et al., 2024). Developing an inquiry laboratory module can engage students through hands-on activities (Partanen, 2022), thus, learning tasks engagement vary in terms of approaches (Yu et al., 2024).

Researchers proposed a solution by developing an Inquiry-based General Chemistry Learning Module for Grade 11

STEM Students. The module include concept on general chemistry. The concepts are based on learning resources such as textbooks and academic websites. The module provides an instruction for students to properly understand the step-by-step process of learning. The module includes learning tasks and activities.

Inquiry-based general chemistry learning module emphasizes the deeper conceptual understanding of each Grade 11 STEM students at Cavite State University-CCAT Campus. It promotes chemistry to students by making it more relatable. The module emphasizes active learning through exploration of ideas and experimentation that can help students to have greater interaction with chemistry and other subject areas. These skills play a vital role not only to the success of academic aspects, but also in more complex challenges of students' future career. It reflects strong foundation for innovation and adaptation for students by formulating questions, hypothesize, and analyze their findings. The focus of interacting with chemistry and integrating this material with other subject matters gives scope to the educational process; in fact, it may contribute considerably to holistic growth and accomplishment.

Methods

Description of the Project

The main purpose of the study is to create an inquiry-based learning module designed for Grade 11 Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) students at Cavite State University - CCAT Campus. The inquiry-based learning module is designed to help students improve their critical thinking skills by teaching them how to solve problems, differentiate between concepts, and enhance their ideas. It also evaluates how to apply of this approach to other general chemistry subjects to make learning more engaging and student-centered, while encouraging students to think critically and independently. The learning module is required to help students understand and

apply the principles of chemical reactions in an engaging and entertaining way. For each topic in the module, there are activities that focus on specific goals (See Table 1). By helping students explain the different types of chemical reactions, these activities ensure they have a thorough understanding of the principles. In order to help students understand the relevance and value of chemical reactions in real-world scenarios, the lessons also incorporate discussions and real-world examples. Additionally, each subject includes practical experiments that allow students to conduct and witness chemical reactions firsthand. This method not only improves their comprehension of the lessons but also fosters critical thinking and helps them develop their lab skills.

Design and Procedures

The researchers utilized a developmental research design as suggested from a research study conducted by Ederon et al. (2024), where it aimed to produce an inquiry-based learning resource material to enhance integrated science abilities. This study was conducted using modules produced by the researchers. Other methods include pre-test and post-test questionnaires and surveys on a Likert scale format as the research instrument.

The researchers distributed the learning modules to the participants, which consist of fifteen (15) Grade 11 STEM students of senior high school at Cavite State University-CCAT Campus Academic Year 2024-2025 for self-study. Prior to the distribution of the module, a pre-test was conducted to measure the preliminary knowledge of the students on the subject. It is a vital part of the research as it serves as the primary intervention on assessing the students' understanding about the General Chemistry subject. Followed by post-test, in which the result was collected and interpreted for data analysis. On the other hand, research surveys were done to support the future development and improvement of the module.

Testing and Evaluation

The respondents were selected using a convenience sampling technique from Laboratory Science High School, specifically the Grade 11 STEM students that have a population of eighteen (18) students wherein three (3) students are not available due to some personal reason. The respondents that gathered from Grade 11 STEM students are fifteen (15) students consisting of eight (8) Male and seven (7) Female students. The selection of participants was made based on time and resource constraints which offered a readily available participants. The researchers choose Grade 11 STEM students because the topic offered was aligned to the topic they have been discussed.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical measures were used and employed to quantify the data and answer the study's problem set. Mean is used to assess the Grade 11 STEM students' mastery of the aspects in critical thinking skills in General Chemistry 1. Standard Deviation is used to get the average of how distant the individual scores are from the mean of the tests. Dependent samples t-test is used to determine whether there are significant differences in their scores before and after the use of the inquiry-based learning module. Likert scale measures the level of agreement or disagreement of the respondents to the content of the learning module. Item analysis is used to determine the students answer per item.

Ethical Considerations

In order to protect the study integrity and the safety of each participant, the researchers followed a number of ethical guidelines when conducting the study. Through the implementation of confidentiality measures, the researchers gave priority to the privacy of students, and institutional data. To protect the participants' identities, for example, all identifiable information was anonymized,

and they were given pseudonyms. Furthermore, every piece of data gathered for the study was precisely recorded, tabulated, and examined by the researchers. No data manipulation was done, and all data processing followed accepted research procedures. These steps were taken to keep the study's credibility, protect participant identity, and ensure compliance with ethical research standards.

Result and Discussion

What are the steps involved in developing an inquiry-based learning module for Grade 11 STEM students?

. . It is consisted of 5 major procedures wherein, information gathering is the first action done by the researcher to prepare all the information needed on developing inquiry-based general chemistry learning module. The procedure involved in the information gathering process include distinguishing objectives, determining data collection methods, analyzing, and organizing the data gathered. This secures a systematic and effective approach to obtaining requisite information (Borges, 2024). The researchers collected various studies about inquiry-based learning techniques and different efficient patterns for instructing students. The second step is designing, wherein, the researchers planned the formatting and sequence of the overall outline of module. Traditional patterns of creating a learning module are compromised however the intensity and difficulty is adjusted by the researchers to meet inquiry-based learning (Indrowati et al., 2022). The third step is the development, wherein, researchers begin the accomplishment of the inquiry-based learning module. During this course of action, consultation to the adviser of target participants is pursued to extend the validity of the product. After that, the inquiry-based learning module is disseminated to the participants alongside with pre-test, post-test and survey to measure the effectiveness of the inquiry-based learning module (Enderon, 2024). Through dissemination, the researchers

distributed the module to the Grade 11 STEM students. The researchers acquired the results through assessment, which is crucial to precede on the final step. The recommendation is the most significant part of developing an inquiry-based learning module since it contains the proposition of the participants for future development of the inquiry-based learning module.

What are the development of Grade 11 STEM students' critical thinking skills? in terms of (a). identifying and defining problems (b) differentiation of concepts (c) idea evaluation and refinement

This study implies a significant difference between the pretest and post-test performances of fifteen (15) Grade 11 STEM students who utilized the Inquiry-Based General Chemistry learning module. Most of the results come from the pretest and posttest that measures critical thinking skills, specifically, in identifying and defining problems (5 items per test), differentiation of concepts (5 items per test), and idea evaluation and refinement (5 items per test). During the pre-test, idea evaluation and refinement got the lowest mean (mean=3.6), followed by identifying and defining problems with (mean=3.9), and the differentiation of concepts (mean= 4.1) got the highest score, which implies that the Grade 11 STEM students are knowledgeable on these skill even without the utilization of learning module. After utilizing the inquiry-based learning module, the result shows that differentiation of concepts (mean= 4.5) got the highest mean and it was followed by identifying and defining problems and idea evaluation and refinement is considered to have the least mean value (mean= 4.3).The researchers utilized t-test to determine the development of Grade 11 STEM students' critical thinking skills. The table showed that differentiation of concepts had the lowest significant difference of -1.33, followed by identifying and defining problems (t= -1.47). The greatest aspect that showed significant difference is the idea evaluation and refinement (t= -2.20), which implies that the

Grade 11 STEM students have developed this skill the most.

What are the suggestions of Grade 11 STEM students for using inquiry-based learning module in topics of General Chemistry?

For the learning module content, one hundred percent (100%) of the participants either strongly agree (53.33%) or agree (46.66%) that the module provides a deep understanding of the chemical reaction and equation, which is a positive indicator. The participants were able to associate the module content to the real-world scenarios in view of the fact that one hundred percent of the participants strongly agree (73.33%) and agree (26.66%). Additionally, ninety-three percent of the participants either strongly agree (46.66%) or agree (46.66%) that the structure of the module is visually appealing, clear and helps them understand the topic better while seven (7%) of the participants are neutral indicating that some participants might not have had a strong opinion on whether the structure of the module was visually appealing, clear, or helpful for understanding the topic.

For the learning module structure, eighty-seven percent (86.66%) of the participants either strongly agreed (73.33%) or agreed (13.33%) that the module contained no grammatical errors, while seven percent (7%) were neutral and another seven percent (7%) disagreed. This suggests that some respondents may have observed a few grammatical errors but did not find them significant enough to justify a "Strongly Disagree" response. Eighty-seven percent (86.66%) of the participants either strongly agreed (73.33%) or agreed (13.33%) that the content was well-organized and structured. However, thirteen percent (13.33%) chose 'Neutral,' indicating that some participants did not have a strong opinion on the organization of the content. Moreover, one hundred percent (100%) of the participants either strongly agreed (73.33%) or agreed (26.66%) that the module emphasized critical thinking through guided and

independent inquiry.

For the learning module engagement, eighty-seven percent (86.66%) of the participants either strongly agreed (53.33%) or agreed (33.33%) that the activities in the module were interesting and helped keep them focused on the lessons, while thirteen percent (13.33%) chose 'Neutral.' Since the majority of responses were positive, the neutral responses may indicate that these participants were not particularly motivated by the activities but did not find them ineffective either. No drastic changes may be needed, but it could be worth exploring the types of activities that might better engage the neutral responders. Eighty percent (79.99%) of the participants either strongly agreed or agreed that the module encouraged them to actively participate through hands-on or inquiry-based tasks, indicating a strong positive response. However, twenty percent (20%) of the participants chose 'Neutral,' suggesting that the hands-on or inquiry-based tasks did not significantly impact their sense of participation. Moreover, eighty-seven percent (87%) of the participants either strongly agreed (60%) or agreed (26.66%) that the inclusion of interactive features was effective in making the learning experience more engaging and enjoyable. However, a small portion (13.33%) chose 'Neutral,' indicating they neither agreed nor disagreed with the effectiveness of the interactive features.

For learning module efficiency, eighty-seven percent (87%) of the participants either strongly agreed (60%) or agreed (26.66%) that they found the module easy to understand. However, a small portion (13.33%) chose 'Neutral,' indicating they neither strongly agreed nor disagreed about the module's ease of understanding. Ninety-three percent (93.32%) of the participants either strongly agreed (66.66%) or agreed (26.66%), suggesting that the majority of participants found the module effective in addressing their questions and enhancing their understanding, particularly in clarifying concepts related to chemical reactions and equations. A small portion (6.66%) chose

'Neutral,' indicating uncertainty about the module's effectiveness in clarifying their questions. Moreover, ninety percent (93.33%) of the participants either strongly agreed (40%) or agreed (53.33%), suggesting that the majority found the module effective in presenting clear, relevant examples for each topic, complemented by visual aids like pictures. However, 6.66% of the participants chose 'Neutral,' indicating they neither agreed nor disagreed about the module providing specific examples.

For the learning module assessment, ninety-three percent (93.33%) of the participants either strongly agreed or agreed, indicating that the majority of participants felt the assessments accurately measured their understanding and effectively evaluated their knowledge. Meanwhile, seven percent (6.66%) of the participants chose 'Neutral,' which suggests that they were either uncertain about the effectiveness of the assessments or did not feel strongly either way. One hundred percent (100%) of the participants either strongly agreed (73.33%) or agreed (26.66%) that the assessments provided an appropriate level of difficulty, were aligned with the learning objectives, and that the criteria for assessment were clear and transparent.

Overall, one hundred percent (100%) of the participants either strongly agreed (60%) or agreed (40%) that they were satisfied with the learning module. Eighty percent (80%) of the participants either strongly agreed (40%) or agreed (40%) that the module provided a higher level of learning than other similar modules, indicating that the majority of respondents felt this module offered a more advanced or effective learning experience compared to other similar modules. However, twenty percent (20%) of the participants chose 'Neutral,' suggesting that a smaller portion of respondents did not feel strongly about the comparison or were uncertain about how this module measured up against others in terms of the level of learning provided. Eighty percent (80%) of the participants either strongly agreed (60%) or agreed (20%) that they would recommend

the module to others, indicating that the majority of participants found the module valuable and beneficial enough to recommend. However, twenty percent (20%) of the participants chose 'Neutral,' suggesting that a smaller portion of respondents were either uncertain or indifferent about recommending the module. Eighty percent (80%) of the participants either strongly agreed (53.33%) or agreed (26.66%) that the module was a valuable use of their time, indicating that the majority of respondents found the module worthwhile and felt it contributed positively to their learning experience. However, twenty percent (20%) of the participants chose 'Neutral,' suggesting that a smaller portion of respondents did not have a strong opinion about the value of the module. Additionally, twenty-six percent (26%) of participants chose 'Neutral' when asked about their interest in taking other inquiry-based learning modules, indicating that they were uncertain or indifferent about pursuing further inquiry-based learning modules.

Table 1. Grade 11 STEM Student Overall Satisfaction on Learning Module

OVERALL SATISFACTION		SA	A	N	D	SD
1	Overall, I am satisfied with the learning module.	60.00%	40.00%	0	0	0
2	This module provided a higher level of learning than other similar modules.	40.00%	40.00%	20.00%	0	0
3	I would recommend this learning module to others.	60.00%	20.00%	20.00%	0	0
4	I feel the learning module was a valuable use of my time.	53.33%	26.66%	20.00%	0	0
5	I would be interested in taking other modules that offer inquiry-based learning.	46.66%	26.66%	26.66%	0	0

Conclusion

Based to the results, the researchers therefore conclude:

1. The steps on developing an inquiry-based general chemistry learning module is consists of 5 major procedures; information gathering, designing, development, disseminate, and recommendation which contains the proposition of the participants for future utilization of the inquiry-based general chemistry learning module.

2. This study showed a significant difference between the pretest and post-test performances of fifteen (15) Grade 11 STEM students who utilized the Inquiry-Based General Chemistry learning module, wherein, the t-test shows that the differentiation of concepts had the lowest significant difference of -1.33, followed by identifying and defining problems ($t = -1.47$), idea evaluation and refinement ($t = -2.20$), which implies that the Grade 11 STEM students have developed this skill the most.
3. Majority of Grade 11 STEM students are satisfied and strongly agree that the inquiry-based general chemistry learning module provides them a deeper conceptual understanding, emphasizes critical thinking through guided and independent inquiry, encourages them to actively participate on inquiry-based tasks, and effective in evaluating their knowledge, while some of them were uncertain about pursuing further inquiry-based learning modules.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, students provided suggestions for future researchers conducting similar studies.

1. Sufficient time for participants to complete the module to avoid rushed responses or incomplete data that could compromise the results' accuracy and reliability;
2. Explain the module to respondents to ensure understanding and minimize errors;
3. The module's content should not be too much nor too less to avoid overwhelming respondents or causing boredom;
4. The module should be well-organized, clear, and incorporating of images and icons to enhance engagement and interactivity; and
5. The module must include all the necessary information for the respondents, as it is inquiry-based

and primarily designed for self-directed learning.

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